

Design of a pre-timed traffic signal at Mokola - Bodija – University of Ibadan Road intersection, Ibadan

ABSTRACT

Traffic congestion is a significant challenge in urban areas, leading to air pollution, travel delays, and safety hazards. This project focuses on the Mokola - Bodija – University of Ibadan Road intersection and proposes a pre-timed control signal to upgrade the existing traffic management system. A traffic survey was executed at the intersection, generating crucial data. The peak hour factor and design hourly volumes were then calculated following established guidelines from the Highway Capacity Manual 2010 (volume 3: interrupted flow). This approach led to the determination of saturation flow rate and cycle length, key parameters for evaluating traffic dynamics. The peak hour was pinpointed between 7:30 a.m. and 8:30 a.m., registering a substantial flow of 3,728 vehicles per hour with a peak hour factor of 0.96. Additionally, design volumes were computed at 1118, 366, 1209, and 1191 vehicles per hour for A, B, C, and D approaches respectively. The collected data underwent verification against the traffic signal warrants outlined in the Manual on Uniform Traffic Control Devices (MUTCD 2003), leading to a positive outcome aligned with Warrant 3. The saturation flow was calculated as 3600, 2400, 4659 and 5760 vehicles per hour for the A, B, C and D approaches respectively with flow ratios of 0.31, 0.15, 0.26 and 0.20 for A, B, C and D approaches respectively.

Keywords: Traffic congestion, pre-timed control signal, Road intersection, traffic flow, Ibadan

1. INTRODUCTION

Traffic congestion is a prevalent issue on road networks, characterized by slower speeds, longer trip times, and increased vehicular queuing, which adversely affect transportation efficiency and societal well-being (Duranton & Turner, 2015). Managing traffic congestion involves rationalizing the costs of improving the transportation system against the benefits of enhanced travel times (Hermann, 2015). Moreover, lifestyle choices and the presence or absence of car ownership also contribute to the subjective experience of traffic congestion (Blunden, 2014).

Traffic congestion has become a major problem in rapidly growing urban areas like Ibadan. Due to urbanization and the increased use of motor vehicles, traffic congestion is getting worse every day (Kumar, M., Kumar, K., & Das, P., 2021). For instance, the Lagos-Ibadan expressway often experiences delays during peak periods, exacerbated by accidents, breakdowns, or disruptions in alternative transportation modes (Blunden, 2014). Understanding traffic flow is crucial, as excess vehicles exceeding the road's capacity can lead to severe congestion.

The relationship between urban land use and traffic congestion is critical in rapidly growing urban areas like Ibadan. Urban road networks are becoming increasingly complex, and the increasing travel demand has outpaced the transportation system's capacity (Yin, R., & Song, X., 2023).

However, the dynamics of urbanization in Ibadan Metropolis have given rise to several challenges, with traffic congestion emerging as a significant problem resulting in accidents and damage to life and property.

The specific objectives of this study are to collect relevant traffic data at the intersection, and design a traffic control system for the intersection based on the gathered data.

The major problem associated with the Mokola - Bodija - University of Ibadan intersection that warrants a pre-timed traffic signal include high traffic volume. The intersection is located in a densely populated area and serves as a major thoroughfare for both urban and rural traffic. This results in high traffic volumes during peak periods, which can lead to congestion and delays.

Another problem is complex traffic movements. The intersection is a four-legged intersection with multiple turning movements, including left turns, right turns, and U-turns. This complexity can make it difficult for drivers to navigate the intersection safely and efficiently.

This study aims to alleviate congestion and improve the traffic flow at the Mokola - Bodija - University of Ibadan intersection area by analyzing traffic patterns and designing a pre-timed traffic control system. The results of this study will have applications for improving transportation efficiency, reducing delays, and minimizing the associated costs for both individuals and the government.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1 Reconnaissance Survey

Reconnaissance was carried out to be familiarized with the general characteristics of the area to assess the situation on the ground before carrying out a detailed survey. It involved evaluating facility types available in the study area, traffic generators in the study area and getting the time elements.

For this report, aerial photographs of the area were taken to see the study area (see Figures 1 & 2). Also, the facility type of road was determined.

Map of Ibadan North showing University of Ibadan

Figure 1: Geographical Location of the Awolowo Intersection (Source: Google Maps)

Figure 2: 3D Aerial View of the Area of Study using Revit, 2017 Software

2.2 Traffic Volume Count

For this research, the length of the sampling period selected was a total of four (4) hours daily for three (3) days using fifteen (15) minute intervals. The typical commuter peak periods included the weekday morning (7:00 – 9:00 am) and the weekday evening (4:00 – 6:00 pm).

2.3 Method Used for Traffic Count

For a span of three days, from Monday, January 20th to Wednesday, January 22nd, an electronic counting board in the form of a mobile application, known as "Traffic Counter," was employed to conduct traffic counts. This app closely emulates the traditional mechanical counting board, featuring a counter mounted on a board to log traffic flow in various directions. Notably, screenshots of the application were captured at fifteen-minute intervals throughout the traffic count duration.

2.4 Peak Hour Factor and Design Hourly Volume

The peak hour factor gauges the fluctuation in demand within the peak hour, calculated as the ratio of the volume observed during the peak hour to the highest flow rate within a specific time segment of that hour.

The peak hour factor for the intersection is given as

$$PHF = \frac{\textit{Peak Hour Volume}}{4 \times \textit{volume during a peak 15 minutes within peak hour}} \quad (1)$$

Design Hourly Volume (DHV) is the traffic volume that is expected to occur during the busiest hour of the day. It was obtained using:

$$DHV = \frac{\text{Peak Hour Volume}}{PHF} \quad (2)$$

2.5 Saturation Flow Rate

The saturation flow was determined from the equation

$$\frac{3600}{\frac{(t_n - t_4)}{(n-4)}} \quad (3)$$

Where:

t_n = time of the last vehicle surveyed

t_4 = time of the fourth vehicle surveyed

n = number of vehicles

2.6 Determination of Cycle Length

Using the equation in the Highway Capacity Manual (volume 3: interrupted flow), for the determination of critical v/c ratio, cycle length becomes:

$$C = \frac{X_c}{\sum \left(\frac{v}{s}\right)_{ci}} \times C - L \quad (4)$$

Table 2: Parameters for determination of cycle length

Parameters	Values	Source
Critical v/c Ratio (X_c)	0.95	Highway Capacity Manual
Lost Time (L)	4 seconds	Highway Capacity Manual

$(\sum_i(v/s)_{ci})$ = Summation of all flow ratios for all approaches

2.7 Yellow Interval

The yellow interval is the amount of time that a traffic signal displays the yellow signal indication. The yellow signal indication warns drivers that the green signal is about to turn red and that they should stop if they are able to do so safely.

The equation below is used to determine the sufficient yellow interval τ_{min} for the intersection

$$T_{min} = \delta + \frac{W+L}{U_0} + \frac{U_0}{2(a+Gg)} \quad (5)$$

Where:

δ = perception time W = Width of intersection L = Length of vehicle

U_0 = Speed limit a = Constant rate of breaking deceleration (m/s²)

G = Grade of the approach g = Acceleration due to gravity (m/s²)

2.8 Allocation of Green Times

The period of time when a traffic movement is efficiently using the junction is known as the effective green time. The total effective green time available was determined using

$$G_{te} = C - L \quad (6)$$

Where:

G_{te} = Total effective green time per cycle, C = Cycle Length, L = Total Lost Time

By dividing the entire effective green time among the several phases in accordance to their saturation flow levels, the minimum overall delay was achieved. The actual green time for each phase was rearranged to become

$$G_a = G_{ei} + l_i - \tau_i \quad (7)$$

Where:

l_i = Lost time for phase I τ_i = Yellow time for each approach G_{ei} = Effective green for each approach

The effective green is given as:

$$G_{ei} = \frac{\left(\frac{v}{s}\right)_i}{\sum \left(\frac{v}{s}\right)_{ci}} \times G_{te} \quad (8)$$

Where:

$\left(\frac{v}{s}\right)_i$ = Flow ratio for each approach $\sum \left(\frac{v}{s}\right)_{ci}$ = Sum of all flow rate

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Road Inventory

The study area was observed as a 3-legged intersection, and traffic wardens controlled the traffic at the intersection at the time of conducting this study. The traffic generators are the Agbowo shopping complex and the University of Ibadan.

3.2 Traffic Count

The result of vehicular counts conducted during the afternoon peak periods on Monday, 20 January 2020, which was observed to have the highest amount of hourly vehicular flow during the traffic volume study, is shown in Table 3 below:

Table 3: Vehicular counts for the morning peak period (Monday, 20 January 2020)

TIME (AM)	A (Veh/15mins)	B (Veh/15mins)	C (Veh/15mins)	D (Veh/15mins)	Total (Veh/15mins)
7:00-7:15	200	60	205	200	665
7:15-7:30	221	65	262	251	799
7:30-7:45	305	84	290	295	974
7:45-8:00	251	90	309	300	950
8:00-8:15	260	95	301	290	946
8:15-8:30	257	82	261	258	858
8:30-8:45	275	68	241	262	846
8:45-9:00	277	70	245	241	833

Figure 3: Graphical representation of total 15-minute traffic volume at the intersection

Figure 3 shows that the highest 15-minute volume, with 946 vehicles, falls on the 75th minute between 8:00 am – 8:15 am.

3.3 Determination of Peak Hour

The intersection's peak hour was identified by summing the four most substantial 15-minute intervals from the traffic count. This approach revealed the hour with the highest traffic volume (Table 4). The volume counts from Monday, 20 January 2020 morning was considered for this.

Table 4: Peak Hour Volume (Monday, 20 January 2020)

Time (AM)	Volume (veh/15mins)
7:15-7:30	799
7:30-7:45	<u>974</u>
7:45-8:00	<u>950</u>
8:00-8:15	<u>946</u>
8:15-8:30	<u>858</u>
8:30-8:45	846
8:45-9:00	833

Highest four consecutive 15-minute counts = 3728 veh/hr

According to Table 4 above, the peak hour occurred between 7:30 am and 8:30 am with a flow of 3728 veh/hr.

3.4 Determination of Peak Hour Factor

The peak hour factor measures the variability of demand during the peak hour. The peak hour factor (PHF) is found by dividing the peak hour volume by four times the peak 15-minute volume. For this study, the period considered was 15 minutes, and the peak hour factor for the intersection is given in Equation 1:

$$PHF = \frac{\text{Peak Hour Volume}}{4 \times \text{volume during peak 15 minutes within peak hour}} \quad (9)$$

$$= \frac{3728}{4 \times 974} = 0.96$$

3.5 Design Hourly Volume

To establish the design hourly volume, the peak hour factor was divided by the total traffic volumes. These values show the traffic volume that is expected to occur during the busiest hour of the day. The values of DHV exceed the total traffic volume on all approaches because the DHV represents the highest expected traffic volume during the peak hour period. In contrast, the total traffic volume accounts for all vehicles over an entire day. It is therefore safer to design for the worst-case scenario.

Table 5: Design Hourly Volume of each Approach

APPROACH	TOTAL TRAFFIC VOLUME	DESIGN HOURLY VOLUME (veh/hr)
A	1073	1118
B	351	366
C	1161	1209
D	1143	1191

3.6 Traffic Signal Warrant

To justify the installation of an upgraded traffic control signal at Awolowo Intersection of UI/Secretariat Road, the result of traffic count was checked against the traffic signal warrant of the manual on uniform traffic control devices (MUTCD 2003). Due to the length of the study, selected warrants (Warrant 3 and 4) were analysed with the data collected. Warrant 3 (peak Hour) and Warrant 4 (Pedestrian Volume) were analysed, but it was observed that the pedestrian

volume was unable to meet the criteria for warrant 4. Therefore, the traffic volume was checked against Only Warrant 3 which yielded positive.

3.7 Determination of Saturation Flow Rate

Using equation (3), the saturation flow rates for each approach are shown in Table 6 below:

Table 6: Saturation Flow Rate for each Approach

APPROACH	SATURATION FLOW (veh/hr)
A	3600
B	2400
C	4659
D	5760

3.8 Flow Ratio

Flow Ratio refers to the ratio of vehicular flow of each approach to the saturation flow rate of the approach considered. In order to be able to determine the cycle length of the proposed upgraded traffic control system (pre-timed traffic signal), the flow ratio is to be used. The flow ratio is an important factor in determining the cycle length because it affects the amount of time that each direction of travel will have to proceed.

$$\text{Flow Ratio} = \frac{\text{Flow Rate}(\frac{\text{veh}}{\text{hr}})}{\text{Saturation Flow Rate}(\frac{\text{veh}}{\text{hr}})} \quad (10)$$

Table 7: Flow Ratio for each Approach and the sum of the flow ratios

APPROACH	FLOW RATIO
A	0.31
B	0.15
C	0.26
D	0.20
SUM	0.92

3.9 Determination of Cycle Length

Using the equation (4) and the values in Table 2

Cycle Length = 125 seconds

3.10 Determination of Yellow Interval

Using equation (5), where:

Perception reaction time (δ) = 2.5 seconds

Width of intersection (W) = 31m

Length of vehicle (L) = 4.5m

Speed Limit (U_0) = 13.89m/s

Constant breaking deceleration (a) = 3.4m/s²

Acceleration due to gravity (g) = 9.81m/s²

$$G = 1$$

$$\text{Yellow interval} = 2.5 + \frac{31+4.5}{13.89} + \frac{13.89}{2(3.4+9.81)}$$

$$= 2.5 + 2.56 + 0.526$$

$$\cong 5.6 \text{ seconds}$$

Therefore, a yellow interval of 5.6 seconds is needed for the intersection

3.11 Allocation of Green Times

Using equation (6), where:

$$C = 125 \text{ seconds}$$

$$L = 12 \text{ seconds}$$

$$G_{te} = 125 - 12$$

$$G_{te} = 113 \text{ seconds}$$

The total effective green time required for the intersection is 113 seconds.

3.12 Actual Green Time

Using equations (7) and (8), the actual green times for each approach are calculated in Table 8

below:

Table 8: Actual Green Time for each Approach

APPROACH	ACTUAL GREEN TIME (seconds)
A	36.47

B	16.82
C	30.33
D	22.96

4. CONCLUSION

The traffic volume study at the Mokola - Bodija - University of Ibadan Road intersection supports implementing a pre-timed traffic control signal system to improve traffic flow. During the peak hour period from 7:30 am to 8:30 am, the traffic flow at the intersection was recorded to be 3,728 vehicles across the A, B, C, and D approaches.

The recommended signal timing parameters for the pre-timed system are as follows:

- i. Saturation flow - The saturation flow rate was computed to be A: 3,600 veh/hr, B: 2,400 veh/hr, C: 4,569 veh/hr, D: 5,760 veh/hr;
- ii. Cycle length – The cycle length was calculated to be 125 seconds;
- iii. Yellow interval – The yellow interval was computed to be 5.6 seconds;
- iv. Effective green time - 113 seconds.
- v. The actual green times were approximately calculated as A: 37 seconds, B: 17 seconds, C: 30 seconds, D: 23 seconds.

Implementing the pre-timed traffic control signal system with these parameters is expected to effectively enhance traffic flow and alleviate congestion at the intersection. This improvement will contribute to a more efficient transportation for commuters and the community.

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